

DO WE NEED A NEW ECONOMIC APPROACH TO THE CREATIVE ECONOMY IN THE DIGITAL ERA?

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Abstract

The economics of creative industries is at the confluence of two streams of change: one due to the widespread adoption of digital technologies and the other in the theories needed to understand their effects. I discuss these changes in terms of paradigmatic shifts and conclude that while digitisation has transformed the distribution and consumption patterns of the arts and culture, the cost of creation of new work has been essentially unchanged. Moreover, industrial economics has made the adaptations needed to understand these changes.

I. Introduction

New technologies affect the workings of the economy but do they change economic thinking? What makes for a paradigm shift has been hotly debated in economics as in science (though admittedly by the relatively few economists with an interest in methodology). In general, methodology provides the 'rules of the game' for assessing a fundamental change that represents a break with that which went before, usually a body of thought or a dominant theory. A paradigm is defined as a philosophical and theoretical framework for formulating and testing theories, which in economics is typically done using statistical or observational data: a paradigm shift occurs when there is a fundamental change in approach or the underlying assumptions, in this case of technology.

Although the term 'paradigm shift' is often over-used, it can be a useful way of thinking about change – change brought about in the 'real world' by the introduction of new technologies, new market structures and players and new business models, as well as other types of change. But are such changes radical enough to cause a paradigm shift in the economic theories used to interpret them or do they evolve? I suggest that the ubiquitous use of what has come to be called platform economics – the microeconomics of two- and multi-sided markets and network effects – calls for this kind of analysis. And where better to apply it than in the context of the creative

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industries which have been profoundly affected by the digital revolution? In this Working Paper I use these ideas loosely to consider the impact of the widespread adoption of digital technologies on the creative industries and to reflect on the change in economists' analysis of those industries.

Digitisation has brought fundamental change to the economics of the creative industries. It has certainly altered the fortunes of some cultural organisations, such as museums and opera houses, which were previously viewed as inevitably sclerotic from the economic point of view and it has enabled new industries to emerge, such as video games. It has fundamentally altered participation and consumption of cultural goods and services as well as production techniques and especially distribution and sales methods. It has enabled the multitude to display their artistic contributions to the world online but has not, however, essentially altered the craft of professional creativeness and the time and investment in human capital needed to produce it. There is a potential threat from AI, which could possibly have significant economic implications, but there has so far been little hard evidence of its economic effects. So, the picture is mixed: there has been a shift in the 'manufacture' or processing and distribution of creative work and in expanded opportunities for reaching the market but the economics of the initial creation of new works remains more or less the same.

The question in the title of this paper was raised for the then so-called 'Information Age' in the book *Information Rules* Shapiro and Varian published in 1999. Their answer was no, we do not need a new economic approach - 'technology changes, economic laws do not': economics is general and powerful and can be applied to any economic activity. Starting in 2000, I taught a course on economics of creative industries and used their book as required reading; it has stood the test of time well and the quote still merits consideration.

In one sense, economics has always done the same thing - analysed supply and demand, the price mechanism and the market economy - certainly since Adam Smith, and some historians of economic thought would go back to Aristotle. The *Wealth of Nations* was written on the cusp of the Industrial Revolution in Great Britain and quite a bit of it is as relevant and readable as when it was written but equally, most of it is not. So, is it the context and the stage of economic development that is the barrier or do we need more and better economic theories than Adam Smith provided us with? And if that applies to Adam Smith, it must do so to any other path-breaking economist.

It is obvious that the economy has changed over time, altering the context in which economic theory operates. The switch from agrarianism to industrial production made huge changes to

people's lives but the basic laws of economics still made sense: there was relative scarcity of resources whose uses were determined by relative costs and prices; some enterprises became large but there were inherent limits to expansion. Now that we live in an information-rich digital economy, we should consider if that still holds true; whether the underlying economic conditions of production have changed fundamentally. For instance, we need to understand the tendency for the increased development of ever-larger dominant multi-national corporations in the digital economy. Although the relative emphasis on microeconomic concepts used by economists has shifted along with changes in technology, we should ask whether the underlying economic laws are still relevant in the digital age.

Another aspect is in macroeconomics: national income accounting requires that industries are defined and measured for their contribution to National Income and for growth. Consistency in reporting is required so that like is compared with like, with the result that National Income Accounting is slow to adapt to change in the structure of the economy. New categories may be needed for new goods and processes but change weakens the ability to make before and after comparisons (see Coyle and Mitra-Kahn, 2017). When the UK introduced the new category of creative industries and the new 'paradigm' of the creative economy, it became difficult to measure growth with the result that unrealistic claims could be made for their economic impact (Towse, 2011). Such changes are basically matters for government statistical offices but the outcome can be important for policy-making and, moreover, statistics are used for lobbying and rent-seeking purposes. Creative industry lobbies have laid claim to attention by national governments and international organisations because the data they produced on their size and growth purported to show they are significant sources of national income and economic growth. These claims have been advanced both in less developed economies with strong artistic and cultural traditions and in post-industrial economies unable to compete with newer manufacturing economies. Initially, at least, the data on which those claims were based were collected and presented in ways that did not conform to best practice National Income Accounting and so could be misleading.

A further aspect in the discussion of the impact of these developments relates to the role of economics in government policy and regulation: we need both microeconomic theories about the response of market economies to creativity and innovation and macroeconomic data on the outcome. In the creative industries, copyright law is a favoured form of regulation alongside cultural subsidies; can the law deliver the benefits to creativity it claims? Has the rationale for subsidies changed? Is competition law, which applies to all types of industries, effective in

a multi-national economy of intangible products? Evidence, not just data, is needed as a basis for policy and to evaluate policy measures in the creative industries.

The paper is organised as follows:

Section II introduces what I call the new paradigms of the economy, the reorientation towards the production and consumption of intangible, ephemeral goods produced electronically, which has ushered in the concepts of the knowledge and/or creative economy. Section III discusses the use of 'old' and Section IV the new economic theories analysing the creative industries and the 'new' business models in the digital economy. Section V turns to the labour markets for creators and performers, the producers of creative goods and services and section VI concludes with some final remarks.

II. 'Paradigms' of the post industrial economy

The decline of heavy industry then of manufacturing led to the use of the term 'post-industrial' economy with its strong reliance on the service economy. These terms reflect the relative size of those sectors in the national income. By the end of the 20th century, reorientation to the 'Information Economy' and the 'Knowledge Economy' had taken place. The former, known as the 'Information Society' and the 'Information Age' in other contexts, followed the increasing spread of in computerisation and the perception of the economic value of data; the latter, espoused in particular by OECD (Organisation of Economic Cooperation and Development), evolved its own research programme on the knowledge economy based on the prominence of human capital.¹ Their shared economic characteristics are the production of goods that are intangible or based on a fundamental input that is intangible (Haskel and Westlake, 2018). Digital goods are easily replicated and effectively become public goods, which with IT as a means of distribution, can be disseminated for a very low or zero marginal cost, typically requiring protection through intellectual property law for the appropriation of value.

Neither public goods nor zero marginal cost were new concepts in economics: public goods have been traced back to Adam Smith and applied to defence, law-making and maintenance of the value of currency as collective goods, but applying them to a broad range of the private sector goods and services is novel. The problem of zero marginal cost had been highlighted by Dupuit (in the context of the optimum toll for crossing a bridge: see Blaug, 1986). The combination of digital technology with the knowledge/information content that underlies

¹ See www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=OCDE/GD%2896%29102&docLanguage=En. For recent OECD publications in this area, see www.oecd.org/going-digital/measuring-the-digital-transformation-9789264311992-en.htm.

the paradigm of the new economy is characterised by the distinction between the creation of content and its delivery. These developments took another direction with the notion of the creative economy and the mustering of the creative industries that is the focus here.

The creative economy

The United Nations, led by UNCTAD (UN Conference on Trade and Development), produced the first *Creative Economy Report 2008* that embraced artistic, cultural, scientific and technical creativity. The *Report* identified economic characteristics that underlie the creative industries: they are 'the cycles of creation, production and distribution of goods and service that use creativity and intellectual capital as primary inputs; constitute a set of knowledge-based activities, focused but not limited to arts, potentially generating revenues from trade and intellectual property rights; comprise tangible products and intangible intellectual or artistic services with creative content, economic value and market objectives' (UN, 2008; 13).² This was based on several prior ways of identifying the creative industries: the term 'cultural' industries (as distinct from 'the arts') had been introduced in France in the 1980s and soon entered the lexicon of UNESCO. Then in 1998, the UK adopted a creative economy programme as a self-conscious means of promoting the UK's perceived leading position in innovation and creativity in the arts and culture.

Before this somewhat unexpected change, the arts in the UK had been 'overseen' by the Office of Arts and Libraries, a very small government department with a narrow scope, reflecting the UK's policy of 'arm's length' administration of state support via special bodies, such as the Arts Council, the Crafts Council and, in a different category again, the BBC (which is an independent corporation financed by a licence fee). The UK model of dealing with the cultural sector was very different from that found in other European countries in which cultural organisations were (and many still are) typically state-owned and staffed by civil servants. The formation of the UK's Ministry of Culture, Media and Sport (DCMS) in 1998 involved marshalling together in to one 'sector' oversight of these arm's length bodies and elements from other departments of the UK government, such as sound recording and film production, which were previously in the domain of the Department of Industry and Trade. It also included taking on some aspects of copyright, which, as discussed below, came to be seen as the lynchpin of the creative industries in the UK (as elsewhere). The motive for this development was almost entirely political but it established the need for a reorganisation of industrial classification in the national income accounts, therefore involving economics. These developments, however, pre-dated

² These developments are discussed more fully in Towse (2019).

the adoption of digitisation in the creative sector and the new business models that accompanied them, a topic to which I return later.

Creative industries in the UK

The Creative Industries Mapping Document published in 1998 by the DCMS, using as its definition 'those industries which have their origin in individual creativity, skill and talent and which have a potential for wealth and job creation through the generation and exploitation of intellectual property'. Later, the intellectual property element was also adopted as one of the criteria by UNESCO and other international organisations, notably by WIPO (World Intellectual Property Organisation). This definition resulted in a list of industries which has several times been revised. In the UK since 2017 it has comprised advertising and marketing, architecture, craft, product design, graphic design, fashion design, film, TV, video, radio and photography, IT, software, video games and computer services, publishing and translation, museums, galleries and libraries, music, performing arts, visual arts and cultural education, which together now define the UK's Creative Economy.³ Initially, the data that DCMS produced were not consistent with established National Income accounting criteria: there had been no previous category in the accounts that included all the newly designated creative industries and what data there were had typically been produced by the industries themselves, which were used to demonstrate their 'economic importance' for rent-seeking purposes.

Eventually the National Statistical Office in the UK stepped in and creative industry data are now routinely handled by it as part of their regular reporting. In 2019 (latest available figures) the Creative Industries accounted for 5.9% of UK GVA, having grown 5.6% between 2018 and 2019. The 'IT, software and computer services' subsector contributed over 50% to this growth.⁴

Digitisation in the creative industries

Although several of the creative industries were quick off the mark to adopt digital methods in their production process, they appear to have been taken by surprise by consumers' ability to gain access to their products without payment. Piracy led to a huge worldwide campaign following the Napster case to pressure national governments and international organisations to increase the scope, term, penalties and enforcement of copyright, which has been done successively over the last 20 or so years. WIPO instigated a programme of measuring

³ See <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/dcms-sectors-economic-estimates-methodology/dcms-sector-economic-estimates-methodology> for full discussion.

⁴ By contrast the 'Cultural Sector' accounted for 1.8% of UK GVA, having increased by 9.5% between 2018 and 2019. See <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/dcms-economic-estimates-2019-gross-value-added/dcms-economic-estimates-2019-provisional-gross-value-added>.

the 'economic value' of copyright in a large number of countries, adopting the underlying and unproven assumption that without copyright these industries would either not exist or would contribute much less to GDP.⁵ The fact that the USA was the only net exporter of copyright works was ignored and institutions were set up in less developed countries (which often have strong music and craft industries), persuading them that this was a route to their economic growth. Once in place, though, payment for foreign cultural content had to be formalised along with that of the local industries.

The involvement of WIPO in the creative industries is another indication of their perceived value in National Income creation in both less developed countries as well as in developed ones. It also highlights the hype that surrounded the creative economy and the supposedly crucial role of copyright in its size and growth. As new business models have developed, at least in some countries, the level and impact of piracy has been muted. Overall, business models have proved more successful in displacing piracy than the technological protections measures that were brought in with much fanfare by WIPO at the end of the 1990s. Indeed, it was left to economists to point out that on the one hand, there is always some level of criminal activity in any economy and the issue is the net gain that can be achieved by increasing penalties and enforcement; and on the other hand, some proportion of piracy would never enter the market as effective demand, as the price of legal use is too high for some consumers (for example, children). Other arguments were also made, including that some piracy is beneficial due to network effects of pirated consumption spilling over to paid demand (Waldfoegel, 2018).

The discourse above lays down the basis for discussing the role of economic theory in understanding of the creative economy, perceived here as representing a paradigm shift due to the digital nature of its products and production processes and the role of the internet in providing access to producers and consumers.

III. Old and new economic theories and creative industries

In previous stages of the economy dominated by agriculture, heavy industries and manufacturing, industry size was tied to land, labour and capital as factors of production, in which the individual enterprise (the firm) reached natural limits through diminishing returns to a factor or to the scale of production, with the consequent effect on costs. The standard economics textbook explanation is that costs would initially fall with an increase in inputs and the scale of production but would eventually rise due to inherent bottlenecks as the enterprise

⁵ WIPO (2003, 2015). Empirical estimates of piracy by Waldfoegel (2018) have shown that overall the effect on output is probably neutral.

got 'too big'. In this 'heavy' economy, producers both created their products and supplied them to the market. Rising costs and inevitable higher prices would eventually kill off demand and the industry would become less profitable, causing investors to switch their capital to other enterprises. Thus, in principle, economic forces would allocate resources efficiently via supply demand and the price mechanism.

A long-recognised exception to this self-regulating scenario is natural monopoly, in which there are no decreasing returns to scale even over a very large output, so that marginal costs never rise above average costs. The theory was traditionally applied to utilities, such as electricity and telephones – industries with high fixed costs of production and an extensive distribution network. The problem for the profit-maximising producer is that marginal cost pricing (the ideal of free marketeers) would not cover long run average costs and so utility industries were typically state-owned or regulated if privatised. The natural monopoly is, however, preserved and regulated in order to maximise welfare: the consumer pays the marginal cost (the lowest possible price) and the sunk or fixed cost of the plant is financed by some formula set by regulators or (as in the case of arts organisations) by a subsidy. In that way, welfare is maximised by regulation that works via the price mechanism. Regulation and privatisation of utilities have also split up the production of the good from the delivery system, for example, the production of electricity from its distribution network. The natural monopoly model has also been applied to cultural goods and services, including theatrical performance and museum exhibition, in which state subsidy is used to cover the fixed costs (Towse, 2019).

There are strong resonances of this model for production in the digital world, in which it is important to distinguish the initial production of content (content creation) from distribution, for example, by internet platforms (Coyle, 2020). Although for many goods and services fixed or sunk costs have not changed much in the production of the 'prototype', digital products are non-rival and non-excludable when they are made available online, hence the case for copyright to 'privatise' what are essentially public goods. On the distribution side, the use of digital technology and the internet has vastly reduced the costs of marketing and delivering content. Digital producers are natural monopolists due to ever increasing returns to scale in distribution. In the digital creative economy, though the model fits, there has been no such established mode of regulation of platforms such as that found in utilities, however. This is an ongoing discussion in economics, see for example, an interview with Tirole.⁶ Only recently has regulation of FAANG (Facebook, Amazon, Apple, Netflix, Google) begun to be on the political agenda. Another

⁶ See <https://qz.com/1310266/nobel-winning-economist-jean-tirole-on-how-to-regulate-tech-monopolies>.

concern, for example on the part of OECD, has been the question of how to regulate multi-sided markets for 'intangible' goods and services (OECD, 2018).

While monopoly is universally regarded as a bad thing and competition as a good thing, regulated natural monopoly is an exception, as are copyright and other types of intellectual property monopolies: awarding exclusive control to the creator is justified in terms of their welfare-enhancing role in stimulating creativity and innovation (Landes, 2020). Schumpeter famously argued that as (temporary) monopoly enables charging a price greater than marginal cost, it provides the entrepreneur with the incentive to innovate and therefore monopoly is necessary for economic growth. He argued that monopoly offers the entrepreneur 'lead time' to capture the returns on her invention before competitors enter the market and compete down the price, coining the phrase 'creative destruction' for the process. Schumpeter's focus was on patents - he omitted to apply it to copyright (Blaug, 2005). It should be said, however, that copyright is a weaker form of monopoly than a patent as it is restricted to copying per se; 'independent' creation is a defence against the charge of unauthorised copying, something that often crops up, for example, in cases of apparent musical 'theft'.

The theory of creative destruction has been applied to the music industry: it has been argued that record labels were vulnerable to 'destruction' because they failed to adapt to digital downloads and streaming as use of the internet spread (Handke, 2010). Creative destruction requires ever more technological innovation and alert entrepreneurs who have the funds to invest. Those who already invested in earlier technology (incumbent firms) are likely to be stuck with it for a while, enabling new entrants to stake their claim in the market. Not every innovation is successfully adopted long term, however: in the creative industries there is some evidence, for instance, that e-publishing is declining while hard copy book sales are rising (Hviid, et al. 2019). On the other hand, some professions in the creative industries have experienced greater 'shock' than others, for example, photography (Williams, 2021); that study showed the increased pressure of oversupply but at the same time, the need for greater investment in human capital to keep up with the demands of new technologies, ways of working and business models placed on them.

These economic theories are well-established, some older than others, and they may be applied to the creative economy. Of course, they were novel in their day and supplanted or challenged 'incumbent' theories. The process of creative destruction also applies to innovation in economic theory!

IV. New economic theories and the creative industries

The digital creative industries are subject to both increasing returns to scale and also to network effects, the combination predicting that they are likely to grow into even bigger natural monopolies. In digital format, there is no limit to the number of consumers or other users who can obtain a perfectly cloned copy of a digital good or join a social media platform and there are no barriers to entry to creating your own website. There is abundance, not scarcity in digital output. The limit in the digital economy is the scarcity of time and attention on the part of consumers/users and their numbers, something understood by Simon with his notion of the 'attention economy' for which *inter alia* he won the Nobel Prize in economics in 1978 (Blaug, 1986).

Network effects are demand-side benefits to both sellers and buyers of goods and services emanating from the uses of online services, such as e-mail and social media sites. Unlike other external benefits, though, network effects can be captured commercially via online markets. The more people who buy the good or use the social media network, the greater the value to others using it and so the greater the value derived from it resulting in the higher their willingness to pay. Moreover, the greater the network benefits, the more valuable it becomes and more people join the network, creating exponential growth. Furthermore, multi-homing – the practice of using several online platforms – amplifies these consumption network effects (Bacache-Beauvallet, 2020). Thus, technological developments have largely overcome possible negative network effects, such as congestion, although bandwidth restrictions may limit their scope.

Benefits can be captured by entrepreneurs as the process of searching for and consuming digital goods and the information provided on people's websites produces online data which can be manipulated electronically to develop individual consumer profiles, which in turn have value to others besides the immediate seller. Discrete websites are amalgamated to provide user profiles and information and sold to other companies for commercial, political and a range of other purposes.

These effects suggest that 'big' is likely to get ever 'bigger': there are no market-based checks to expansion. That is a paradigm shift in technology with strong economic implications. Since governments accept that with regulation, natural monopoly can reap the benefits of lower costs, this suggests they apply the same principles to platforms (Coyle, 2022; Haskel and Westlake, 2022).

Platform economics: Two-/multi-sided markets

A change in economic organisation that has evolved quickly in the digital economy is that of two- or multi-sided markets, although as with so many such developments, there are some

precursors. One of the oldest two-sided market models in the creative economy was that of advertised-based commercial radio (and later TV), whereby the consumer tolerates the ads in order to receive free access to programmes with the broadcaster as the platform. Advertisers buy slots according to the putative audience, thus financing the service. A similar arrangement has been applied also to ad-financed 'free' streamed music. These models have evolved with online services, offering multiple products and experiences. The key change is complementarity and the fact that network effects produce demand-side externalities associated especially with online consumption. They are the source of positive benefits to both sellers and buyers of goods and services as well as to users of online services, such as e mail and social media sites. As argued above, there are no diminishing returns to scale or long run scale diseconomies to set an eventual limit to their size or number, at least on the supply side. Tastes change on the demand side, however, and attention moves away – the consumer side of creative destruction, perhaps.

Multi-sided markets have several different groups of users on a platform, enabling the use of price discrimination. A 'classic' example is a dating club, which attract more men than women, so price is differentiated to offer incentives to women to join. The same market form also applies to video game console entrepreneurs in the games industry who need to appeal to both game developers and players. The platform adopts pricing and other strategies to keep multiple sides engaged, thereby internalising externalities across the various participants.

Subscriptions to large, bundled repertoires of song, book and film titles have emerged from these market forms enabling consumers to avoid the advertisements. These aggregations are no longer in the hands of the 'original' industry, however, but are done by the platforms. These changes in the way buying and selling works are novel but they were not developed specifically for the digital economy, although digitisation and mass use of platforms is what has nurtured them.⁷ Economists have acknowledged these business models and incorporated them into industrial economics: the question is whether these changes require a revolutionary paradigm shift in economic thinking or an evolutionary change. I would opt for the latter interpretation.

V. The creator and the creative industries

So far, the focus of this chapter has been on industrial organisation. The first step in the chain of production in the creative industries (as the DCMS quote above makes clear) is the 'creator' – an artist, craftsperson, author or performer. The creative process involves skill and talent, long

⁷ In 18th century England, the local Assembly Room acted as a platform, offering dances, concerts a library and other facilities. The more the 'right sort' of people took part, the greater the value to other members. I belong to a private subscription library in Penzance today.

training, experimentation and time, at the end of which a work is produced whose success on the market is uncertain. The greater the novelty, the higher the risk.⁸ The risk and cost of production of novel creative work – the time spent in experimentation, the acquired knowledge and experience and the cost of materials used – is in the first instance borne by the creators, who then have to engage with cultural entrepreneurs (industry) to get the work to market. Once established, a commercial enterprise may finance further work by offering a longer term contract with or without an upfront payment, thereby sharing risk to different degrees.

Copyright law protects creators and performers from unauthorised use of their work as they approach the market. Contracts are then negotiated between the parties concerned with the author (creator/performer) and publisher (record label, film company et al) in a deal that exchanges the right to produce and market a product based on the underlying copyright. The terms of the contract reflect the extent of competition in the market, both among the creators and the publishers. Generally speaking, the creator, unless she is a superstar, has the weaker bargaining position and that is exacerbated by the economic organisation of the industry: the more concentrated is the industry, the weaker her position in relation to the enterprise with the result that new entrants may be pressured to sign away rights to their work.

The implications for creators of the economic organisation of creative enterprises are analysed by Caves (2000) who applied the branch of economics known as contract theory to the creative industries, building up a picture of contract complexity from the simple 'handshake' contract between an artist and art gallery, to those in the film industry involving multiple skills and personnel. Caves' proposition is that the transfer of the rights to creators' and performers' works is required by the industry (rather than a licence to use them for a limited time) in order to protect sunk investment from later hold-ups in a sequential chain of production.⁹

All contracts offer terms governing the use of the work and the reward due, though they may take different forms. In some creative organisations the creator or performer has an employment contract, either permanent or temporary, which means the rights to work done under that contract belong to the employer. Other contracts range from a transfer of all rights to a work for a single fee (a 'buy-out') to a royalty contract, in which rights may be split up and negotiated separately, for example, the film rights of a book title may be retained by the author in a publishing deal and contracted separately (as in the case of JK Rowling). Different contracts

⁸ Strictly speaking, uncertainty is when no probability can be assigned to the outcome, while risk carries a known (or knowable) probability. These terms are used loosely (as here) to indicate the general position. Experience can change uncertainty into risk.

⁹ Caves' work predates the adoption of digitisation in the creative industries. It would be interesting to see the effect it has had over the ensuing 25 years.

offer different incentives and rewards and also influence, or are influenced by, the structure of the industry. In some, employment contracts are the norm, for example, for players in an orchestra, while a pop group would have a royalty deal transferring the rights to their performance to a record label. There are many mixed examples as well but the underlying principles are the same.

Impact of digitisation on creators' labour markets

Contractual arrangements and contracts have changed over time in the arts and creative industries: royalty contracts are now the norm in musical and literary publishing, though only since the last century, before which flat fee payments which bought out all rights were common (Towse, 2017). The growth of state subsidy for the arts led to secure employment for some performers in orchestras and opera and dance companies, although not for all. Insecure funding leads to creators and performers having to face many temporary contracts and low incomes, as reported in surveys of their labour markets. For a while, royalties from copyright were threatened by piracy but the threat was always greater for the industry side than the artist, since for most, a royalty deal did not (and does not) constitute a substantial part of their income (Di Cola, 2013; Kretschmer et al, 2019; IPO, 2021). Superstars are likely dominate artists' labour markets even more in the digital era due to the expanded markets the internet offers.¹⁰ The greatest impact of digitisation on artists' earnings, though, has been the transfer of rights by the publisher to a platform to use creators' work in a deal in which the creator has no say. Although ad hoc arrangements have been made to pay the creator, for example, a streaming rate, these are not contractual arrangements. Bearing in mind that many initial contracts were (and often still are) for the life of copyright (which varies for authors and performers but for both extends well beyond their lifetime), many find themselves locked-in with only moral rights available to control subsequent use made of their work.

To combat those developments, the UK government is following the example of other countries, notably the USA and also some in the EU, by considering the introduction of statutory reversion clauses into contracts, known as 'use it or lose it' and 'best seller' clauses, which would enable artists who believe the record label they are contracted to is not treating them appropriately to pull out of the contract after a specified period and seek to improve the terms with another or with the same producer (IPO, 2021).

¹⁰ Between 2014 and 2020 the top 1% of artists accounted for 78–80% of music streams, and the top 10% for 98%. Only 0.4% of artists achieved more than 1 million streams per month (IPO, 2021).

The digital economy has affected the economic organisation of creative labour markets as well as that of product markets in the creative industries. The cost of creation of the underlying content remains basically similar regardless of the means by which it is delivered to the consumer, though it has been argued that adoption of AI might change that (Peukert, 2019). While those costs are more obvious in labour markets for artists in creative industries for which formal training is a necessity, it is also the case that informal training, 'learning by doing', involves investment in human capital that takes time as well as in the necessary capital equipment. Time has an 'opportunity cost' of the amount that could be earned in an alternative occupation while learning takes place. The question of the potential effects of AI, however, hangs in the balance.¹¹

In some industries, digital technologies appear to have provided a complement to access to creative work rather than a substitute for it (Bakshi and Throsby, 2014), but there has been little work on the demand side (the CMA Report inevitably noted that consumers had benefitted considerably from easier and cheaper access to music via streaming). On the supply side, social media platforms have opened up the possibility for creators to offer their work directly to the public and many do so, both professional and amateur (in fact, that distinction is increasingly becoming difficult to maintain).¹² There has been some research on this showing that those self-publishers who succeed online are offered contracts with enterprises in industries, such as publishing and games (Hviid, 2019) as well as in the music industry. There is an irony here in that the early perception of the internet was that it enabled a 'long tail' of market participation by creators counteracting the superstar tendency.¹³ An 'unintended' outcome is that self-publication online by creators has reduced the search costs (A&R) of enterprises in the creative industries enabling them to select the successful ones, thus reducing their risk in marketing the work. There is some suggestion that this has led to improved contractual arrangements for those who are approached this way; the topic requires further research. Digitisation has therefore altered the status quo in various ways.

Whatever the impact of these changes on the way creators' labour markets are organised, it does not seem to call for new economic theories to explain the underlying logic of contracting. Moreover, copyright law, which has been adapted to the digital economy, is probably not as

¹¹ AI itself requires human direction and human capital investment. Just as sound and lighting engineers have come to be regarded as part of the creative workforce, the same could happen for those in AI. It certainly calls for more research.

¹² For example, digitisation has led to a major increase in the number of artists releasing music, up from 200,000 in 2014 to 400,000 in 2020 (CMA, 2022).

¹³ There has been some confusion in the use of the concept: some use it to mean that in a statistical distribution of incomes in an occupation, there are more individuals to be found in the middle; others use it in the sense of the superstar effect introduced by Rosen (1981), who showed that increasing market size favoured a few top earners.

significant as is claimed as an economic incentive since the critical point lies in the contractual arrangements made rather than the law itself.

VI. Final remarks

The question this paper tries to address the extent to which the paradigmatic shift in the creative economy due to the adoption of digital technologies has impacted on the economic theories we use to understand these changes. The question is discussed in the context of the creative industries, which have been considerably affected by these changes. Is economic theory in fact so general and so robust that it can prevail over changes in economic organisation regardless of the technologies adopted, as Shapiro and Varian suggested?

The switch to an economy of abundant supply in which network effects produce data as a joint product has had significant impact on many parts of the creative economy. It has enabled sizeable external, even public goods, effects ('spillovers') to be internalised by private enterprise. These technological shifts have led to the growth of very large online platforms, which have quickly come to dominate markets in many of the creative industries. It seems that 'traditional' industrial economics has been successfully extended to cope with the digital creative economy and that existing economic concepts, such as natural monopoly, have been adapted for analysing it. Economic theory has responded by evolution rather than by revolution. So, the answer is that Shapiro and Varian were, on balance, correct.

The creative economy consists of both the creation of content and its delivery and the effects of digitisation on each have differed. While digital content can be disseminated to vastly expanded markets for virtually zero cost to the supplier, the cost of content creation likely remains more-or-less unchanged. For many of the activities of the older parts of the creative economy that are building-based, and therefore subject to the limitations of time and space (such as the performing arts and museums), visitors are now able to participate online via digital means. I can go to my local arts centre in a small town in the UK and pay to watch a narrowcast live performance ('event cinema') from the Metropolitan Opera in New York (and there is even excess demand for that) but the performance also can be replicated 'as though live' in various ways. I can 'view' an exhibition from the British Museum in the same way. With improved technology at home (surely only a step away) I could view these events without going out, thereby lifting restrictions of time and space. The closure of live performance venues and live activities due to the measures taken to control Covid-19 provides a natural experiment in audience behaviour: having had to participate only online for several months, are consumers returning to live events? It remains to be seen what the long-term impact of the lockdown has had on

the taste for home consumption of creative goods – another possible paradigm shift, research that is waiting to be done.

The initial creation of creative goods and services, however, remains fundamentally unchanged with high fixed costs due to the human capital and time required to create them in the first place, regardless of the means whereby they reach the audience. Although digital technologies may be used to assist the creative process, they have not been a substitute for the human effort involved and likely have increased the need for investment into how to apply them. Artificial intelligence may change that: some music has been generated that way and ‘played’ electronically (raising awkward questions for copyright law). The contention is that digitisation has so far not really altered the cost of professional content creation, although it has increased overall supply by others and, perhaps more significantly (see CMA, 2022), has enabled the resurrection of masses of older content that now competes directly for consumers’ attention, the commodity that is ultimately in short supply.

Indeed, limitations of time and attention on the part of consumers may be more significant factors than cost on the production side, even though people are more accustomed to multi-tasking – listening to music while travelling, working or reading and engaging with social media etc. The market repeatedly demands more content, both new and old. The most serious competition for new work, therefore, probably comes from the repeated reuse of earlier work. By contrast to online consumption in the home, though, games enthusiasts flock to large venues and pay entrance fees to observe professional gamers playing video games remotely, with the potential for scarcity of places in the space. Diminishing returns to home consumption may eventually set in, something cultural economists should be considering.

All this suggests that we currently live in a dual creative economy, in which the time and human capital needed for creativity is more or less unchanged while the uses to which creative work are put have changed fundamentally with digitisation and the internet. At bottom, people still want to experience the arts and be entertained and there are many talented creators and performers ready to offer their services, despite the relatively low average reward. Those services are supplied in both traditional and new modes of delivery.

Some institutional arrangements require root and branch change, however. Given the positive feedback of internalised externalities on the digital economy, regulation of monopoly requires rethinking: for instance, which side of a multi-sided market should be regulated? (Tirole, 2017). Governments failed to grasp the changed nature of the information economy, taking a *laissez-faire* stance waiting to see how things evolved; by the time it was clear that there are few (if any)

limits to the expansion of platforms, it was too late to apply national law and taxation measures to control their unwanted effects, which have to be tackled at the supra-national level. A question also hangs over whether copyright law is capable of adaptation. Digitisation has made copyright excessively complicated as it struggles to adapt, so much so that many individual creators for whom its protection is designed fail to either understand or apply it to their work. These types of regulation, however, can only work on an international basis, requiring extensive trade negotiations, which are slow and expensive.

Economics has the means to explain these trends with platform economics firmly established in the economics agenda, though it is unfortunately not always adopted in the solution of problems thrown up by new technologies and business models.¹⁴

¹⁴See Stickler (2015) and Towse (2020) on the US Copyright Board debate over rate-setting.

References

- Bacache-Beauvallet, M. and Bourreau, M. (2020) 'Platforms' in Towse, R. and Navarrete Hernández, T. *A Handbook of Cultural Economics* 3rd edition: 421-9.
- Bakhshi, H. and Throsby, D. (2012) 'New technologies in cultural institutions: theory, evidence and policy implications', *International journal of cultural policy*, 18(2), 205-222.
- Blaug, M. (1986) *Great Economists Before Keynes*, Cheltenham UK and Lyme US: Edward Elgar.
- Blaug, M. (2005) 'Why Did Schumpeter Neglect Intellectual Property Rights?', *Review of Economic Research in Copyright Issues*, Volume 2(1).
- Caves, R. (2000) *Creative Industries: Contracts between Art and Commerce*, Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Competition and Markets Authority (CMA) (2022). Available at <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/music-streaming-report-published>.
- Coyle, D. (2020) *Markets, State and People*, Princeton and Oxford, Princeton University Press.
- Coyle, D. and Mitra-Kahn, B (2017) *Making the Future Count* available at <http://global-perspectives.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2017/10/making-the-future-count.pdf>.
- DiCola, P. (2013) 'Money from Music: Survey Evidence on Musicians' Revenue and Lessons About Copyright Incentives', 55 *Arizona Law Review* 301. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2199058>.
- Handke, C. (2010) 'The Creative Destruction of Copyright - Innovation in the Record Industry and Digital Copying'. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=1630343> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1630343>.
- Haskel, J and Westlake, S. (2018) *Capitalism Without Capital*, Princeton and Oxford, Princeton University Press.
- Haskel, J. and Westlake, S. (2022) *Restarting the Future*, Princeton and Oxford, Princeton University Press.
- Hesmondhalgh, D., Osborne, R., Sun, H. and Barr, K. (2021) *Music creators' earnings in the digital era* available at <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/music-creators-earnings-in-the-digital-era>.

[Hviid, M.](#), Izquierdo-Sanchez, S. & [Jacques, S.](#) (2019) '[From publishers to self-publishing: disruptive effects in the book industry](#)', *International Journal of the Economics of Business*. 26, 3: 355-381.

Intellectual Property Office (IPO (2021) *Music Creators' Earnings in the Digital Era*, Newport, Intellectual Property Office.

[Kretschmer, M.](#) , Gavaldon, A. A., [Miettinen, J.](#) and [Singh, S.](#) (2019) [UK Authors' Earnings and Contracts 2018: A Survey of 50,000 Writers](#). Documentation. CREATE, Glasgow.

Landes, W. (2020) 'Copyright' in Towse, R and Navarrete Hernández, T. *A Handbook of Cultural Economics*, 3rd edition: 116-28.

OECD (2018) *Rethinking Antitrust Tools for Multi-Sided Platforms* available at www.oecd.org/competition/rethinking-antitrust-tools-for-multi-sided-platforms.htm.

Peukert, C. (2019) 'The next wave of digital technological change and the cultural industries', *Journal of Cultural Economics*, 43(2), 189-210.

Rosen, S. (1981) 'The Economics of Superstars', *American Economic Review*, 71: 845-58.

Shapiro, C. and H. Varian (1999) *Information Rules*, Harvard Business School Press: Boston.

Strickler, D. (2015) 'Royalty Rate Setting for Sound Recordings by the United States Copyright Royalty Board: The judicial need for independent scholarly economic analysis', *Review of Economic Research on Copyright Issues*, 12(1/2); 1-15.

Tirole, J. (2017) *Economics for the Common Good*, Princeton University Press. For his views on monopoly regulation, available at <https://qz.com/1310266/nobel-winning-economist-jean-tirole-on-how-to-regulate-tech-monopolies>.

Towse, R. (2011) 'What We Know, What We Don't Know and What Policy-Makers Would Like Us to Know About the Economics of Copyright' *Review of Economic Research on Copyright Issues*, vol. 8 no.2 December; 101-120.

Towse, R. (2017) 'Economics of Music publishing: Copyright and the Market', *Journal of Cultural Economics*, 2017, 41 no 44; pp 403-20.

Towse, R. (2019) *A Textbook of Cultural Economics* 2nd edition, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Towse, R. (2020) 'Dealing with digital. The Economic Organization of Streamed Music'. *Media, Culture and Society*.

Williams, P., McDonald, P. and Mayes, R. (2020) The Impact of Disruptive Innovation on Creative Workers: the Case of Photographers, *Creative Industries Journal*, 14, 2, :130–151.

World Intellectual Property Organisation (WIPO) (2003, 2015) *Guide to Surveying the Economic Contribution of the Copyright-based Industries*, Geneva, WIPO.

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